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Membrane Reflection Coefficient

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IN a recent communication¹ dealing with the membrane selectivity and reflection coefficient, σ , earlier defined by Stavermann², it has been shown by Singh *et al*¹ that the idea advanced by Shrivastava *et al*³, refuting the justifiability of the criterion for the description of the selectivity of ideally semipermeable membranes even when interaction between the permeating solute and solvent is considered, has no validity. They have also examined, separately, the permeation of an electrolyte mixture solution containing solutes 1 and 2, wherein interaction between various constituents of the solution is either (a) completely ignored or (b) considered, in the light of non-equilibrium thermodynamics⁴. In their analysis¹ they have concluded⁵ that when permeation of solute, is completely checked σ_1 and σ_2 are unity only when

$$\Delta C_1 = \Delta C_2 = \Delta C/2 \quad \dots (1)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the solutes 1 and 2 respectively. The analysis, probably, has been applied to the case of dilute solutions where the laws of osmotic pressure hold good.

The above conclusion arrived at by the authors¹ appears to be misleading which would be apparent from what has been discussed below.

Equation (10) (Ref. 1), by substitution of the results from equation (11) (Ref. 1), presents only a specific case when the components 1 and 2 are equal in concentrations, each being equal to $\Delta C/2$, as has been observed by the authors⁵. The above observation, read with equation (11) (Ref. 1) also compels us to recognise $\Delta\pi_1 = \Delta\pi_2 = \Delta\pi/2$ (which obviously follows when we equate $\Delta C_1 = \Delta C_2 = \frac{1}{2}\Delta C$) and in that event the discussion of the authors¹ converges to the discussion of only a very selected and simple case of a solution having solutes of equal concentration. It is only due to this fallacy or the use of this specific rider that a factor $(\Delta C/2\Delta C_1)$ appears in the second term of the

second parentheses of equation(10). Similarly $(\Delta C/2\Delta C_2)$ appears in the second term of the third parentheses of the same equation. Presumption of such a situation deprives this finding of the authors¹ of assuming the general character. The discrepancy in equation (10) (Ref. 1) may, however, be circumvented by modifying the approach as discussed below :

$$\Delta\pi_1 = RT\Delta C_1$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\Delta\pi}{\Delta C} = \frac{\Delta\pi_1}{\Delta C_1} = \frac{\Delta\pi_2}{\Delta C_2} = \frac{\Delta\pi_1 + \Delta\pi_2}{\Delta C_1 + \Delta C_2} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\Delta\pi}{\Delta C} = \frac{\Delta\pi_1 + \Delta\pi_2}{\Delta C}$$

$$\text{or } \Delta\pi = \Delta\pi_1 + \Delta\pi_2 \quad \dots (3)$$

($\Delta C = \Delta C_1 + \Delta C_2$ will be applicable to the system under consideration¹). It may be noted that ΔC_1 and ΔC_2 may be equal, but not necessarily ; it may be different as well. In fact ΔC_1 may assume any value irrespective of the value of ΔC_2 without affecting the dilute nature of the solution. This, certainly, is a more generalized approach. In each case the condition $\Delta C = \Delta C_1 + \Delta C_2$ will hold so long as the dilute nature of the solution is retained. Thus it would be clear that our equation (3) is not equivalent to equation (2) of K.S. - R.S. (Ref. 1) which makes use of a specific rider discussed above.

Coming to the last portion of the paper¹, after equation (17) (Ref. 1), dealing with the situation where interaction between the solvent and the solutes has been taken into consideration, J_v has been shown to be given by equation (18) (Ref. 1). Equation (2) will still be valid under the situation of the system discussed in the paper¹. Under the circumstances, we find that with the modification as suggested in equation (2) the forms of equations (19-20) (Ref. 1), obtained from equation (18) (Ref. 1), remain unaltered while those of equations (21-23) (Ref. 1) undergo a little change. In equation (21) (Ref. 1) the term $\Delta C/2\Delta C_1$, outside the parentheses of the second part of the second term (associated with $\Delta\pi_1^*$) of the r.h.s. will vanish. Similarly the term $\Delta C/2\Delta C_2$ outside the parentheses of the third portion of the second term (associated with $\Delta\pi_2^{**}$) of the r.h.s. will also vanish. As regards equations (22-23) (Ref. 1) σ_1 and σ_2 will assume the

following forms ^{***} respectively. For smooth read-

* Which has been erroneously printed as $\Delta\pi$.

** Erroneously printed as $\Delta\pi^2$.

*** The printing mistakes and the omissions in the original equations have been taken into consideration in writing our present equations.

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ability we reproduce the corrected equations for σ_1 and σ_2 .

$$\sigma_1 = \left[\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \pi_1} \right]_{J_v=0, \Delta \pi_2=0}$$

$$= - \frac{\left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(\bar{C}_s)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(\bar{C}_s)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \frac{\bar{V}_w}{(\bar{C}_s)_1} \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} - (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} - \bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} - \bar{V}_w^2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} \right]}{\left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} \right.}$$

$$\left. + (\bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} + \bar{V}_w^2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} \right]} \dots (4)$$

and

$$\sigma_2 = \left[\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \pi_2} \right]_{J_v=0, \Delta \pi_1=0}$$

$$= - \frac{\left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(\bar{C}_s)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(\bar{C}_s)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + \frac{\bar{V}_w}{(\bar{C}_s)_2} \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} - \bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} - \bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} - \bar{V}_w^2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} \right]}{\left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} \right.}$$

$$\left. + \bar{V}_w (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial(\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} + \bar{V}_w^2 \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial \Delta \mu_w} \right]} \dots (5)$$

They are found to be, separately, equal to unity without taking recourse to $\Delta C_1 = \Delta C_2 = \Delta C/2$, i.e., without the application of the specific rider used by the authors¹. It can be emphasised, therefore, that the reflection coefficient of a membrane remains unaffected from the concentrations of the different individual components of the system so long as the solution preserves its dilute nature. The result, thus obtained, in the above generalised manner, also embodies the findings of the authors¹ whose case refers to only one particular situation. This is also in conformity with equation (16) (Ref.1) of the authors⁵. Thus for the condition $\sigma_1 = 1$ and $\sigma_2 = 1$ equation (16) (Ref. 1) is written as

$$\sigma \Delta C = \Delta C_1 + \Delta C_2 = \Delta C$$

so that

$$\sigma = 1$$

It has to be noted that for σ to be unity the condition $(J_s)_1 = (J_s)_2 = 0$ has to be satisfied for either conditions, i.e., whether we deal with the interacting situation or the non-interacting situation, as mentioned by the authors¹.

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Effect of Third Component on the Phase Separation of Triethylamine and Water System—A Comparative Study

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THE effect of 1 : 1 electrolytes on the phase separation temperature (PST) of a solvent mixture of 40% by weight of triethylamine (TEA) in water is studied, using data from literature¹⁻¹⁶, along with a number of new measurements of the PST using standard procedures¹⁷.

Results and Discussion

Effect of Anion: Table 1 shows the effects of alkali metal and ammonium halides on the PST of TEA—Water mixture. It is seen that the smaller anions (Chloride and Bromide) give negative ΔT , where ΔT is the PST of the ternary mixture minus the PST of the binary solvent mixture. The bigger